

Stability Constants of Chelate Compounds of 2-Hydroxyacetophenone with Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II) in Aqueous Solutions

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The stability constants of metal chelates of 2-hydroxy-acetophenone with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) have been determined in an aqueous solution of ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄) at 27 ± 0.1° by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adapted by Calvin and Melchior. The experimental data are treated by different computation methods and the average values of the stability constants are reported. The results conform to the Irving-Williams stability order.

Although several studies have been reported for metal chelates of salicylaldehyde, with which 2-hydroxyacetophenone is structurally similar, very little work has been carried out on metal-2-hydroxy-acetophenone chelates. So far, the stability constants of only copper(II)¹ and iron(III)² chelates of 2-hydroxyacetophenone in aqueous media have been reported. The present communication describes the results of pH-titration studies on copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chelates of 2-hydroxyacetophenone in aqueous solution of ionic strength of 0.1 M (sodium perchlorate) at 30 ± 0.2°.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Hydroxyacetophenone was prepared by Fries migration of phenyl acetate in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The product was separated by steam distillation and purified by distillation under reduced pressure (b.p. 100°/15 mm). All other reagents used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade. The solutions were prepared in water twice distilled over alkaline potassium permanganate from an all-pyrex unit. Carbonate-free solution of sodium hydroxide was prepared by the method of Allen and Low³. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared as described by Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁴.

A Beckman Expanded Scale pH-meter, Model 76, was used for pH measurements. A special glass electrode (0–14 pH range) was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. The pH meter was standardized against the buffer solutions of standard potassium hydrogen phthalate (*M*/20) and borax (*M*/100).

The Calvin and Melchior's⁵ pH-titration method was used to determine the stability constants in the present work : 40 ml. of a perchloric acid solution (0.0075*M*) containing 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.005*M*) was titrated in the absence and in the presence of the metal ions (0.0004*M*) with a standard (0.1*N*) sodium hydroxide solution from a microburet.

1. D. D. Perrin, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 741.
2. A. Ågren, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 39.
3. N. Allen and G. W. Low, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1933, **5**, 192.
4. K. E. Jabalpurwala, K. A. Venkatachalam and M. B. Kabadi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.
5. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

Each titration mixture was made 0.1M with respect to sodium perchlorate. All the titrations were done under purified nitrogen gas in a pyrex beaker thermostated at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Figure 1 shows the titration curves obtained.

Figure 1. : Potentiometric titrations of 2-hydroxyacetophenone with 0.1N NaOH
 in absence of metal ions ;
 in presence of Co(II) ions ;
 in presence of Ni(II) ions ;
 in presence of Cu(II) ions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The acid dissociation constant, pK_a , of 2-hydroxyacetophenone was obtained from the pH value corresponding to the calculated half-neutralization point in the titration of 2-hydroxyacetophenone in the absence of metal ion. The pK_a value of 9.98 obtained here is in fair agreement with those reported earlier by Perrin¹ and Magnusson *et al.*⁶

The results of the present work show that copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) ions form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates with 2-hydroxyacetophenone. In order to evaluate the stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of these complexes, the formation curves for the metal-ligand systems were calculated using Figure 1. For each system, the values of Bjerrum's formation function⁷, \bar{n} , at various pH values were calculated from the horizontal shift of the metal titration curve relative to the reagent titration curve. In view of the high ligand-to-metal ratio used in each case, \bar{n} is given by the ratio of this horizontal shift to the total metal ion concentration. The concentration of free ligand, $[L]$ (where L represents the anion of 2-hydroxyacetophenone), at any pH value, was calculated from the known concentration of

6. L. B. Magnusson, C. Postmus, Jr. and C. A. Craig, *ibid.*, 1963, **85**, 1711.

7. J. Bjerrum, 'Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution', P. Haase, Copenhagen (1941),

2-hydroxyacetophenone and its pK_a value. Figure 2 shows the plots of \bar{n} against pL for the metal systems studied.

Figure 2 : Plots of \bar{n} against pL for metal-ligand systems

Co(II) ;

Ni(II) ;

Cu(II).

The values of $\log K_1$ and those of the overall stability constants, $\log \beta_2$, of the 1 : 2 chelates were obtained from Figure 2 using the following relations.

$$\log K_1 = (pL)_{\bar{n}=0.5} \quad (1)$$

$$\log \beta_2 = 2(pL)_{\bar{n}=1.0}$$

The $\log K_2$ for the copper chelate was obtained as the value of pL at $\bar{n} = 1.5$. Since the formation curves do not extend up to $\bar{n} = 1.5$ in nickel and cobalt systems, $\log K_2$ values for these chelates were obtained as the difference :

$$\log K_2 = \log \beta_2 - \log K_1 \quad \dots (2)$$

These values are shown as Bjerrum's half-integral values in Table 1.

In view of the small difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in all three systems studied, the \bar{n} and pL data were treated by the correction term and the least squares methods of Irving and Rossotti⁸. By using the least squares method the following eq. (3) was solved algebraically to obtain the mean values of the constants. In order to obtain some information

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)} \beta_2 - K_1 \quad \dots (3)$$

about the spread of these mean values, the mean value of K_1 was substituted into eq. (3) and values of β_2 corresponding to the \bar{n} values used in calculations were evaluated. Then the mean of these values of β_2 was substituted into eq. (3) to calculate values of K_1 at $\bar{n} < 1$. The final average values of K_1 , K_2 and β_2 together with their spreads are given in Table 1 which also includes the average values of the constants obtained by the correction term method.

TABLE 1

Stability constants of 2-hydroxyacetophenone complexes in aqueous medium

Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	Method of evaluation
(H ⁺)	9.98			
Cu(II)	6.55	5.21	11.80	Bjerrum's half-integral method
	6.48	5.30	—	Correction term method
	6.49 ± 0.02	5.25 ± 0.07	11.74 ± 0.05	Least squares method
Ni(II)	4.42	3.02*	7.44	Bjerrum's half-integral method
	4.50	2.82	—	Correction term method
	4.36 ± 0.02	$2.84 \pm 0.12^*$	7.2 ± 0.10	Least squares method
Co(II)	4.22	2.90*	7.12	Bjerrum's half-integral method
	4.20	2.89	—	Correction term method
	4.20 ± 0.06	$2.84 \pm 0.14^*$	7.04 ± 0.08	Least squares method

* values calculated by difference.

The values of the stability constants reported (Table 1) are the concentration stability constants. Although the values obtained by the least squares method would be more acceptable, it may be seen that the half-integral values also are quite representative values of the stability constants.

The order of stability observed is $\text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co}$. This is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁹.

Comparison of $\log \beta_2$ values shows that copper chelate is appreciably more stable than nickel and cobalt chelates. This might be due to the difference in preferred configuration between copper, nickel and cobalt. The former might be forming a square planar complex while the latter two might be forming tetrahedral complexes with 2-hydroxyacetophenone.

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Received December 23, 1970

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